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Social Network Application in Building the Personal Brand of Vietnamese Young People

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Abstract

Research on the application of social networks in building personal brands of Vietnamese young people is approached by the research team in terms of: frequency of Vietnamese youth using social networks, understanding and current status of Vietnamese youth using social networks. Use social media to build your personal brand. The research was carried out through literature review and sociological investigation. The research results show that the current level of young people using social networks is quite high (4.28 points on the Likert 5 scale), up to 53.3% of the respondents use social networks over 4 hours per day. The survey subjects also showed the need for personal branding (2.66 points on the Likert scale 3) and showed interest in building a personal brand with a personal mark (3.68 points on the Likert 5 scale). However, in the 10 content of personal branding according to Saokim Brank (2021), only 2 contents "Be yourself" and "Build consistent words and images" scores represent the level of implementation, and the remaining contents are only shown at the desired level. From the research results, the authors made some exchanges and discussions with the hope that young people will use "Social Networks" more effectively in building personal brands.

Keywords: Social Network, Personal Brand, Personal Branding, Vietnamese Youth

1. Raised the issues

Vietnam is one of the countries with a fast development speed in information technology, the number of people using the Internet and social networks is large and increasing. According to statistics, by January 2020, Vietnam has the number of Internet users up to 68.17 million people (accounting for 70% of the population), the number of social network users is 65 million people (accounting for 67 % population) (Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, 2022).

Building a personal brand is becoming easier and easier, especially for young people with flexible tools such as the Internet, smartphones to connect and social networks, community group activities, YouTube, and livestream channels, are used to spread self-image and messages. That is also the reason hot boys, hot girls, influencers are becoming famous all over social networks. Previously, the communication range of individuals was limited by geographical distance, but today, through social networks, each person can connect a circle of online relationships with each other. The wider the circle of connection, the greater the impact on each individual.

Building a personal brand to assert yourself and stand out from the crowd is the desire of many people, especially young people. In connection with the popularity and influence on young people of the social networking system in recent years, the use of social networks to build a personal brand is an effective and pervasive method in the community. In this study, the authors focus on the following topics: The level of use of social networks by Vietnamese youth; The most used social networks by young people, time and purpose of using social networks; The benefits and limitations of using social networks; Young people's interest in the benefits of personal branding; Consider the level of implementation of personal branding with 10 contents according to SaoKim Branding (2021).

2. Social networking and personal branding from social networks

2.1. Social networks and social networks' characteristics

In today's modern life, social networking is a phrase that is quite familiar to everyone. A social network can be understood as a website or online platform with many different formats and features, making it easy for people to connect from anywhere. Social networks can be easily accessed from many means and devices such as computers, phones (Thin, N.V., 2021).

Social network operates on the Internet platform with features such as: Chat, e-mail, movies, voice chat, file sharing... via social networks, users can share photos, personal views or looking for friends and partners. Although social networks have different names, functions, and usage, they share the same characteristics: (i) Users must create profiles and have their own accounts, (ii) Many users link to each other through names, email addresses, nicknames, Social networks will connect user accounts to individual and organizational accounts, (iii) Posted and shared content in social networks are up to users to decide on images, sentences (<https://hieuluat.vn>, 2022).

2.2. Personal brand

There are many different interpretations of the concept of personal branding. Your personal brand is the sum total of what you choose to present to the world. Simply put, a personal brand includes everything people evaluate about you: Appearance, personality, career, attitude to life, values contributing to society (Linh, L., 2020).

Personal brand is the perception or impression of an individual that is widely and consistently recognized by the public. It can be a combination of how they see that individual in real life, how the media portrays an individual, and the impression people get from information about that individual available online. Personal branding is rooted in people's minds about an individual (Dung, D.T., 2021).

A personal brand is the sum total of all impressions, beliefs and perceptions about an individual. For people who do jobs that require a lot of exposure to the public such as actors, singers, and stars, personal branding is an indispensable part. Besides, personal branding is very important to an audience - publishers (Rentracks.com.vn).

Thus, it can be understood that a personal brand is the sum total of all impressions, beliefs and perceptions that the public perceives an individual. Personal brand is the image of a person in public, including how people perceive your appearance, personality, lifestyle, and values that you contribute to society.

2.3. The benefits of building a personal brand on social networks

Social networks can be used anywhere, as long as there is a smart electronic device such as a phone, ipad, laptop or on a computer with an internet connection. Social networks allow users to share stories, articles, personal ideas, post photos and videos, and announce activities and events online or in the real world. Social networking on the web helps users connect with people living in different lands, in other cities or around the world (ictnews, 2019).

Using social networks to build a personal brand has many benefits such as: (i) The individual is known and remembered more; (ii) Easily build and expand surrounding relationships; (iii) Become more confident; (iv) Speech also becomes more reliable, more weighty; (v) Individuals will appear denser online; (vi) The individual

may have some control over how people see him/herself; (vii) Individuals can easily express opinions, give valuable advice; (viii) Many opportunities for cooperation and work will come (Thao, V., 2022).

Personal branding will help each person understand themselves better, increase their confidence and assert themselves. Successful personal branding also means that the individual has a useful tool for self-control. Building a personal brand on social networks also helps individuals create social transactions and relationships, thereby helping individuals easily develop their work and create a long-term development platform.

2.4. Building a personal brand on social networks

According to SaoKim Branding (2021), in order to build a personal brand, it is necessary to: (i) Position yourself; (ii) Build consistent language and images; (iii) Connect with influencers; (iv) Receive a recommendation; (v) Use professional images; (vi) Build valuable content; (vii) Shine in one's own way; (viii) Utilize social networks to develop personal brands; (ix) Public speaking; (x) Be yourself.

In which to take advantage of social networks to develop personal brands, it is necessary to understand that social networks are a tool with incredible power and influence when building a personal brand. Facebook, LinkedIn, Youtube, Twitter, Instagram, are places where potential customers may be present. Therefore, the appearance of an individual on social networks with quality content will help people see the value of that person more (SaoKim Branding, 2021).

3. Research methodology

To examine the study, the authors used desk research and sociological investigation methods. The data will be aggregated and analyzed using Excel software tools.

By the desk-based research method, the authors collect and synthesize relevant documents and articles, thereby clarifying the concepts and characteristics of social networks, personal brands, and the benefits of building personal branding on social networks, personal branding content through social networks. From the accessible issues, the research team built a survey form on Google drive, the survey questionnaire focused on survey questions to clarify the research contents and objectives.

After building a preliminary survey, the team conducted a test interview with 10 survey participants. Opinions from test subjects were synthesized to complete the official survey form, then the research team sent the complete survey link (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf2rG3TUrfvwyToAQrY4cJbD0-Pzh3WWDIZMt4wmP1rHTFw/closedform>) to young people. Within the framework of the research, the authors focused on sending survey questionnaires to high school students and university students in Vietnam via social media such as facebook, zalo, email.

The method of sociological investigation by survey is conducted by the research team based on two methods, namely convenience sampling method and "snowball" method, which is the next object-finding method based on suggestions or introductions of the subjects just surveyed. Through the survey, the author team collected 435 votes. The survey data was synthesized and statistically analyzed using Excel software, from which to analyze and demonstrate the research problem.

With questions designed according to the Likert scale, when assessing the level of statements, the author determines the distance value and the mean value, specifically:

With a 5-level Likert scale:

Distance value = (Maximum - Minimum) / n = (5-1)/5 = 0.8

Meaning of levels:

1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree/Very Dissatisfied/Very Disinterested

1.81 – 2.60: Disagree/ Dissatisfied/ Disinterested

2.61 – 3.40: No opinion/ Moderate

3.41 – 4.20: Agree/ Satisfied/ Interested

4.21 – 5.00: Strongly agree/Very satisfied/Very interested

With a 3-level Likert scale:

Distance value = (Maximum - Minimum) / n = (3-1)/3 $\approx$ 0,66

Meaning of levels:

1.00 – 1.66: Not necessary/ Disagree/ Dissatisfied/ Disinterested

1.67 – 2.32: No opinion/ Moderate

2.33 – 3: Necessary/ Agree/ Satisfied/ Interested

4. The survey results

The number of survey participants is 435 people, of which 322 women (accounting for 74%), 110 men (accounting for 25.3%) and 3 people who do not want to be specific (0.7%).

Figure 1: Level of use of social networks by survey respondents

Source: The survey results

Regarding the level of use of social networks, out of 435 survey participants, 217 people (49.9%) answered that they regularly use social networks, 141 people (32.4%) use social networks quite a lot, 63 people (14.5%) use Social Media at a normal level, respectively 11 people (2.5%) and 3 people (0.7%) think they use little or no use Social Networks. With the convention of 1 point being not used and 5 points being used a lot according to the Likert 5 scale, the average score on social network usage is 4.28 points, which shows the level of social network usage. Youth associations (survey participants) are at a fairly high level of usage.

Figure 2: The most used social networking sites of the respondents

Source: The survey results

Among 435 people, 410 people use Facebook (94.3%); 323 people use Tiktok (74.3%) and 301 people use Youtube (69.2%); Instagram and Zalo have the same number of users at 291 or 66.9%; Twitter with 55 users (12.6%).

Figure 3: Time spent using social networks in a day of respondents

Source: The survey results

With 435 people surveyed, 232 people use social networks more than 4 hours a day (53.3%), 176 people use social networks from 2-4 hours a day (40.5%), 27 people using social media for less than 2 hours per day (6.2%).

Figure 4: Purpose of using social network of respondents

Source: The survey results

With 435 survey participants, 409 people use social networks for entertainment (94%); 376 people use social networks to update information (86.4%); 362 people use social networks to connect and communicate (83.2%); 346 people use social networks to study (79.5%) and 214 people use social networks to share and confide (49.2%). In addition, there are 12 people using social networks for other purposes such as working and trading (2.8%).

Figure 5: The benefits that survey respondents receive when using social networks

Source: The survey results

Among 435 survey respondents, 389 people think that using social networks will help them relieve stress (89.4%); 378 people think that using social networks will help them easily collect documents and information (86.9%); 367 people think that using social networks will help them connect with people easily (84.4%); 325 people think that using social networks will help them learn many soft skills (74.7%). In addition, some people think that social networks bring other purposes such as making money, trading easier.

Figure 6: Limitations that respondents suffer when using social networks

Source: The survey results

With 435 people surveyed, 237 people think that using social networks will lead to insomnia (54.5%), 215 people think that using social networks will reduce interaction between people (49.4%), 202 people think that using social networks will affect their privacy (46.4%), 161 people think that using social networks will cause cyber violence (37%). In addition, some people believe that social networks bring other limitations such as time consuming, harmful to health, affecting user behavior.

Figure 7: Number of survey respondents who have ever done personal branding

Source: The survey results

Of the 435 people surveyed, 122 have done personal branding (28%); 313 people have not done personal branding (72%). This is understandable, because the survey target is young people, so the use of social networks is still mainly for entertainment, updating information, learning, connecting and sharing stories.

Figure 8: Survey respondents' opinions on the necessity of building a personal brand

Source: The survey results

Of the 435 people surveyed, 313 think personal branding is necessary (72%), 98 have no opinion (22.5%) and 24 think it is unnecessary. (5.5%). According to the 3-level Likert scale, the average score of the need for personal branding is 2.66 points, this score shows that young people (survey participants) are assessing the need for personal branding.

Figure 9: Survey respondents' interest in the benefits of personal branding

Source: The survey results

Regarding the benefits of personal branding, 358 people are interested in the benefits of easily building and expanding relationships around (82.3%), 317 are interested in becoming more confident (72.9%), 313 people are interested that many cooperation and work opportunities will come to them (72%), 250 people are interested that their words will become trustworthy, have more weight (57.5%), 229 people are interested that they will be known and remembered more (52.6%), 214 people are interested that they can easily express their opinions , gave valuable advice (49.2%), 174 people are interested in how they will have some control over how people see themselves (40%), 89 people are interested in how they will appear denser online (20.5%). However, there are also a few people (0.5%) who are not interested in the benefits of personal branding.

Figure 10: Respondents' interest in building their own personal brands

Source: The survey results

Regarding building a personal brand bearing their personal imprint, out of 435 people surveyed, 117 people (26.9%) are very interested, 114 people (26.2%) are interested, 163 people (37.5%) are moderately interested, 28 people (6.4%) and 13 people (3%) are not interested and very disinterested, respectively. According to the 5-level Likert scale, the average point about being interested in building a personal brand with a personal impression is 3.68 points, which shows the level of interest of young people (the respondents) for personal branding.

Regarding the implementation of 10 personal branding contents according to SaoKim Branding (2021), with 3 levels of survey: *Not implemented; Have a desire to perform; There is implementation*. And the 1-point convention is not implemented; 2 points is there is a desire to perform; 3 points is done. The results are summarized in the following table:

Table 1: About the implementation of personal branding content

No.	Personal branding content	Perform		Expect to perform		Do not perform		Mean	Evaluation level
		Total	%	Total	%	Total	%		
1	Position yourself	140	32,2	269	61,8	26	6	2,26	b
2	Build consistent words and images	182	41,8	222	51	31	7,1	2,35	a
3	Connect with influencers	118	27,1	282	64,8	35	8	2,19	b
4	Get a promotion	121	27,8	289	66,4	25	5,7	2,22	b
5	Use professional images	125	28,7	277	63,7	33	7,6	2,21	b
6	Content building	132	30,3	266	61,1	37	8,5	2,22	b
7	Shine your own way	150	34,5	256	58,9	29	6,7	2,28	b
8	Take advantage of social media	136	31	268	62	31	7	2,24	b
9	Talk to the crowd	135	31	270	62,1	30	6,9	2,24	b
10	Be yourself	212	48,7	208	47,8	15	3,4	2,45	a

With evaluation value: a. Perform; b. Expect to perform; c. Do not perform

Source: Calculation from survey results

According to the results in Table 1, in the personal branding content, the technique "Be yourself" is performed the most by the respondents – 212 people have done it, corresponding to 48.7%, the average score is 2.45 points at the level where this content is implemented; Next is "Building consistent words and images" – 182 people have implemented corresponding to 41.8% of the average score of 2.35 points in the implementation level. Young people were also aware of "Be yourself" and "Build consistent words and images" these are two factors with average scores showing the level of performance, which also shows that young generation highly appreciate being themselves and building words and images in building a personal brand.

Besides, "Receiving a recommendation" has the highest number of people who want to do it is 289 people (66.4%), followed by the content "Connect with influencers" 282 you want to do, but only 118 people have done it, so although this content is interested, the average score of this content is at the lowest level of 2.19 points (at the level of desire). It can also be seen that young people also want support from influential people in building their personal brand, but due to the young age, the relationships are not many, the access to those who have influence is also a limitation of young people.

The least used content is "Building content" with 37 people (8.5%), "Connecting with influencers" with 35 people (8%) saying they don't do the technique. This. The results also show that in 10 content of personal branding according to SaoKim Branding (2021), there are 8 new contents that stop at the level of desire to implement and the average score according to the survey results ranges from 2.19 – 2.28 points. The content "Leveraging social networks" has 136 people doing it (31%), having a desire to do it, 268 people (62%) and 31 people (7%) not doing it, the average score of this content is 2.24 points at the desired level of performance. Therefore, the author conducted a survey to further survey the level of awareness of the respondents about the view "Social networks make building a personal brand easier", the survey results are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Respondents' opinions on the view "Social networks make building Personal Brands easier"

Source: The survey results

Regarding the opinion of "Social networks make it easier to build a personal brand", out of 435 people surveyed, 151 people (35%) strongly agree, 147 people (34.1%) agree, 124 people (28.8%) are neutral, respectively 6 people (1.4%) and 3 people (0.7%) disagree and strongly disagree. With the convention according to the 5-level Likert scale, the average score with the view "Social networks make personal branding easier" according to the survey results is 3.98 points, showing the level of agreement of young people (survey participants) with the above opinion.

5. Some exchanges and discussions

Successful personal branding also means that you have a useful tool for self-control. The author's survey shows the influence of social networks on today's life, the importance of building a personal brand, specifically:

The level of use of social networks by young people today is relatively large, nearly 50% of them regularly use it, and today Facebook is still the most commonly used website (94.3% of the respondents using Facebook). In addition, over 50% of young people use social networks for more than 4 hours a day, and the main purpose is for entertainment (94%), updating information and connecting (83.2%). The use of social networks also gives young people many benefits such as helping them relieve stress (89.4%), easily collect documents and information (86.9%), connect people easily (84.4%), but social networks also have many shortcomings and limitations such as making them lose sleep (54.5%), reducing interaction between people (49.9%), and affect their privacy (46.4%).

Regarding personal branding, the survey results show that the majority of respondents have not done personal branding (72%). However, the survey respondents showed the need for personal branding over 72% also said that personal branding was necessary (reaching 2.66 points on the Likert 3 scale). At the same time, the survey results show that they are interested in building a personal brand with a personal mark (3.68 points on the Likert 5 scale).

Survey subjects also showed interest in the benefits of personal branding such as easy building, expanding relationships around (82.3%), becoming more confident (72.9%), many opportunities for cooperation and work will come to them (72%). Most of the survey respondents are interested or very interested in building a personal brand bearing their own imprint (more than 90% from moderate to very concerned).

Regarding the 10 contents of personal branding according to SaoKim Branding (2021), most of the survey subjects (almost over 50%) have the desire to implement the 10 proposed contents, while only less than 10 % does not do these things. In which the content "Be yourself" and "Building consistent words and images" were of interest to

you, according to the survey results, the average score with these two items is 2.45 and 2.35 points. The other content shows that young people have the desire to do it. Especially, the results recognize that young people want to “*Get a recommendation*” and “*Connect with influencers*”. Although the content “*Using social networks*” has an average score of 2.24 points at the desired level, the majority of young people agree with the view that “*Social networks make building a brand easier than ever before*” with a score of 3.98 points according to the survey results.

With the rapid development of today's online platforms, using social networks to build a personal brand is a useful tool that young people can access. To become an influencer in a particular field and gain many advantages, you need to build a suitable roadmap. According to the survey results, 28% of young people have done personal branding, up to 72% think it's necessary, and only 2 out of 10 content building personal brands follow SaoKim Branding (2021) has implementation. It can be seen that, from thinking to acting, it needs to be defined more clearly, specifically and appropriately:

- “*Be yourself*” is constantly improving to become more useful and better. You need to “*position yourself*”, create value for yourself, spend time monitoring and listening to comments from people around you to improve yourself, this is the core value that helps you develop for a long time and sustainable.
- “*Building consistent words and images*”, the images, words, and phrases you use should show respect for the language they represent. Personal information needs to be screened and selected to use “*Professional Images*” and implement “*Content Creation*” to express your personality and unique style. “*Shine in your own way*”, people with personality, style, differentiation, but value, who are impressed with what you do, and are oriented to the surrounding community.
- The number of friends who have the desire to “*Get a recommendation*” with the highest number in the survey, also shows that young people want to be expressed, want to be affirmed and get recognition. Building a personal brand also requires you to have power, to have credibility. Leadership will come from your talent. “*Speaking in front of a crowd*” is a way to help you express your views and witness. Any brand needs time to develop, patiently, persistently take care and care for its brand, also needs to show goodwill, know how to generate ideas and share exchanges so that everyone can see their own goals.
- On the issue of “*Connecting with influencers*” according to the survey, the average score of 2.19 is the lowest score. Young people also need to be facilitated more, also need support and connections from influential people, mentoring and support to create conditions that help them grow up, succeed and also become influential. And you also have to create opportunities for yourself, actively contact and seek out influential people in your field to be able to shorten the distance to your own success.
- Facebook, Instagram, Youtube or Tiktok ... are all popular social networking platforms that you can use to build your personal brand. You need to choose the right Social Networking platform to step by step implement content with a roadmap in building your own brand. Besides, you can use social networking platforms at the same time, because each platform will have its own advantages and disadvantages. You need to base on your preferences and needs to choose the right platform for you.

The study “*Application of social networks in building personal brands of Vietnamese youth*” has examined some aspects of the current status of social network use, assessed the benefits and limitations of using the network. Vietnamese youth society. At the same time, the level of implementation of personal brand building of Vietnamese youth was reviewed with 10 contents according to the approach of SaoKim Branding (2021), including content related to taking advantage of social networks, and opinions about the application of social networks in building personal brands. However, there are still many aspects that can continue to be considered such as evaluating the effectiveness of the application of social networks, the process to follow to be able to build a successful personal brand through social networking sites or factors affecting the decision to use social networks to build a personal brand... This study is considered a premise for approaching further studies on these contents.

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